

***Salmonella* Typhi Vi polysaccharide conjugate vaccine protects older infants and young children against typhoid fever**

John A. Crump, MB ChB, MD, DTM&H¹

Win Thandar Oo, MB BS, MMedSc²

¹ Centre for International Health, University of Otago, Dunedin, New Zealand

² Department of Microbiology, University of Medicine 1, Yangon, Myanmar

Corresponding author: Prof. John A. Crump, Centre for International Health, Otago Medical School, University of Otago, PO Box 56, Dunedin, 9054, New Zealand. Tel +64-3-479-9460, Email: john.crump@otago.ac.nz

Word count: 700

References: 12

The past decade has seen remarkable progress in our understanding of the scale of the global typhoid fever problem,¹ the alarming emergence in South Asia of extensively drug-resistant *Salmonella* Typhi threatening effective treatment,² and with the World Health Organization (WHO) pre-qualification of typhoid conjugate vaccine,³ a new tool to prevent disease. In *The Lancet*, Qadri and others report the analysis to 18 months follow-up of a cluster-randomized trial of the WHO pre-qualified *Salmonella* Typhi Vi polysaccharide tetanus toxoid conjugate vaccine (Vi-TT) (Tybar[®] TCV, Bharat Biotech International Ltd, Hyderabad, India) among infants and children aged 9 months through <16 years in densely populated and highly mobile urban area of Mirpur, Dhaka, Bangladesh.⁴ Compared with the SA 14-14-2 Japanese Encephalitis vaccine control group, Vi-TT conferred 85% (97.5% CI: 76%, 91%, p<0.0001) total protection. Notably, both total and overall vaccine protection was significant in all vaccinated age groups, including among those aged <2 years, where robust anti-Vi IgG responses were also observed. The vaccine was well tolerated, and no serious vaccine-related adverse events were identified.

So what do we take away from this important trial? Total vaccine protection in the Mirpur study was comparable to the Vi-TT vaccine efficacy recently reported from smaller, individually randomized trials to 12 months follow-up in Kathmandu, Nepal,⁵ and to 18 months follow-up in Blantyre, Malawi,⁶ at 81.6% (95% CI: 58.8%, 91.8%, p<0.001) and 80.7% (95% CI: 64.2%, 89.6%, p<0.0001), respectively. Collectively these trials show that Vi-TT provides a high level of protection across distinct geographic settings up to 18 months of follow-up. Continued follow-up of participants is needed to understand longer term efficacy, including whether booster doses may be needed. Notably, the Mirpur study provides evidence for protection of infants and

children from 9 months through <2 years of age, an age group for which the older attenuated *Salmonella* Typhi Ty21a and unconjugated Vi polysaccharide vaccines were not licenced. This finding is critical because in settings of high overall typhoid fever incidence, typhoid incidence and occurrence among infants and children aged <2 years can be very high.⁷

The ability of typhoid vaccines not only to prevent disease but to reduce *Salmonella* Typhi transmission is pertinent to typhoid control, including elimination thinking.⁸ Of two cluster-randomized trials of unconjugated Vi polysaccharide vaccine, one done in Kolkata, India,⁹ where all persons aged ≥ 2 years were vaccinated showed 44% (95% CI, 2%, 69%) protection of unvaccinated members of Vi vaccine clusters, whereas another in Karachi, Pakistan,¹⁰ vaccinating those aged ≥ 2 through ≤ 16 years showed no evidence of herd protection. As the sole cluster-randomized trial supported through the Typhoid Vaccine Acceleration Consortium,¹¹ the possibility that the Mirpur study would provide insights into Vi-TT indirect protection against typhoid fever has been greatly anticipated. However, the Mirpur study was not powered to detect an approximate 20% level of herd protection, so indirect protection was consigned as a pre-specified secondary objective. Power for this objective was further compromised by the COVID-19 pandemic. Follow-up ended early at 18 months, and the plan to target the primary analysis to the inner 80% of clusters, a strategy that showed promise in a re-analysis of the Kolkata unconjugated Vi polysaccharide vaccine trial,^{9,12} reverted to a traditional whole cluster analysis.⁴ Patterns of typhoid transmission can vary substantially by setting and may have considerable influence on the ability to demonstrate herd protection, if present. For example, if transmission occurs mostly in 'short cycles' by fecal contamination of

food or water within the household, the ability to confirm indirect protection may be relatively greater than in settings where 'long cycle' transmission predominates, for example through fecal contamination of extensively distributed drinking water or food. In the latter circumstance, *Salmonella* Typhi from unvaccinated clusters, or from outside the study area entirely, could penetrate deeply into vaccinated clusters infecting unvaccinated cluster members. In future the authors plan to undertake the pre-specified analysis of persons residing in the inner core of clusters where contamination from unvaccinated populations may be less likely. The typhoid community will await the results of this analysis with great interest, although if negative, we must recognize that the Mirpur study lacked power to detect reasonable levels of herd protection from Vi-TT and look to future studies to address this important question.

Conflict of interest statement

JAC received support from the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation funded Typhoid Vaccine Acceleration Consortium (TyVAC; OPP1151153). WTO declares no competing interest.

REFERENCES

1. GBD 2017 Typhoid and Paratyphoid Collaborators. The global burden of typhoid and paratyphoid fevers: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2017. *Lancet Infect Dis* 2019; **19**: 369-81.
2. Klemm EJ, Shakoor S, Page AJ, et al. Emergence of an extensively drug-resistant *Salmonella enterica* serovar Typhi clone harboring a promiscuous plasmid encoding resistance to fluoroquinolones and third-generation cephalosporins. *MBio* 2018; **9**: e00105-18.
3. World Health Organisation. Typhoid vaccines: WHO position paper - March 2018. *Wkly Epidemiol Rec* 2018; **93**: 153-72.
4. Qadri F, Khanam F, Liu X, et al. Protection by vaccination of children against typhoid fever with a Vi-tetanus toxoid conjugate vaccine in urban Bangladesh: a cluster-randomized trial. *Lancet* 2021: this issue (please update citation).
5. Shakya M, Colin-Jones R, Theiss-Nyland K, et al. Phase 3 efficacy analysis of a typhoid conjugate vaccine trial in Nepal. *N Engl J Med* 2019; **381**: 2209-218.
6. Patel P. Safety, immunogenicity, and effectiveness of typhoid conjugate vaccines in Malawi, symposium 93, 69th American Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene Annual Meeting. *Am J Trop Med Hyg* 2020; **103 (suppl 5)**: 226.
7. Sinha A, Sazawal S, Kumar R, et al. Typhoid fever in children aged less than 5 years. *Lancet* 1999; **354**: 734-7.
8. Stanaway JD, Atuhebwe PL, Luby SP, Crump JA. Assessing the feasibility of typhoid elimination. *Clin Infect Dis* 2020; **71 (suppl 2)**: S179-84.
9. Sur D, Ochiai RL, Bhattacharya SK, et al. A cluster-randomized effectiveness trial of Vi typhoid vaccine in India. *N Eng J Med* 2009; **361**: 335-44.

10. Khan MI, Soofi SB, Ochiai RL, et al. Effectiveness of Vi capsular polysaccharide typhoid vaccine among children: a cluster randomized trial in Karachi, Pakistan. *Vaccine* 2012; **30**: 5389-95.
11. Meiring JE, Gibani M, TyVAC Consortium Meeting Group. The Typhoid Vaccine Acceleration Consortium (TyVAC): Vaccine effectiveness study designs: Accelerating the introduction of typhoid conjugate vaccines and reducing the global burden of enteric fever. Report from a meeting held on 26-27 October 2016, Oxford, UK. *Vaccine* 2017; **35**: 5081-8.
12. Ali M, Sur D, Kanungo S, et al. Re-evaluating herd protection by Vi typhoid vaccine in a cluster randomized trial. *Int Health* 2020; **12**: 36-42.